

Usability Evaluation Process for Domain-Specific Language

You are being invited to participate in the research "Usability Evaluation Process for Domain-Specific Languages: an evaluation survey", under the responsibility of the Phd Student Ildevana Poltronieri, under the guidance of Professor Avelino Zorzo and Professor Maicon Bernardino.

You will participate in a survey that will analyse the Usability Evaluation Process for Domain-Specific Languages. The information obtained through this research will be confidential and we will ensure the confidentiality of your participation. Thus, the disclosed data will not allow any identification.

Your participation is voluntary and if you decide not to participate or you want to cancel your participation at any time, you have the absolute freedom to do so.

Even without having direct benefits in participating, indirectly you will be contributing to the understanding of the phenomenon studied and to the production of scientific knowledge.

This survey is composed of four main sections: the first section for Respondent Identification, the second Perceived Usefulness questions, the third Ease of Use questions and the finally section with three open questions.

In this study we will ask you to respond 17 questions. Your participation in this study will require approximately 20 - 30 minutes.

- To take this survey, you are advised to consult the Usability Evaluation Process for Domain-Specific Language at <http://www.lesse.com.br/usa-dsl/>

If you experience any problem, please report to Ildevana Poltronieri - ildevana@gmail.com

STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT

By answering this survey, you agree to permit the researcher to use and disclose the anonymous information provided as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences, and blog posts
2. I understand that my participation in this research survey is totally voluntary and that declining to participate involves no penalty or loss of benefits. I may withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that I may decline to answer any question that I am not comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researcher if I have any questions about the research survey. I am aware that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will maintain the data collected in perpetuity and may utilize data for future academic work.

4. By clicking the button below I freely provide consent and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as outlined above and provide consent to the researchers to use my information in conducting research. I also confirm that I am of legal age to fill in this survey.

***Obrigatório**

Respondent Identification

1. Name and Surname

2. E-mail

3. Name of Institution or Company

4. Role that best describes your job at institution or company *

5. Time of experience in your role (in years) *

6. Country *

**Perceived
Usefulness
(PU)**

Perceived Usefulness is defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance".

7. PU1. The documentation provided by the Usa-DSL Process helps me understand what should be done. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

8. PU2. The Usa-DSL Process helps me understand how to perform a DSL usability evaluation. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9. PU3. The elements that make up the Usa-DSL Process help me understand what the Process proposes. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

10. PU4. The Usa-DSL Process improves the quality of planning, execution, analysis and report with regard to DSL usability evaluation. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

11. PU5. Although Usa-DSL process is long, its benefits outweigh. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

12. PU6. Overall, I find the Usa-DSL Process is useful in performing usability evaluation for DSL. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Perceived Ease
of Use (PEoU)

Perceived Ease of Use is define as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort".

13. PEOU1. The Usa-DSL Process is objective. I often do not become confused when using it. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

14. PEOU2. Usa-DSL Process is easy to use for fully document elements of a usability evaluation for DSL. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

15. PEOU3. The process flow is easy to use when performing a usability evaluation for DSL. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

16. PEOU4. The process has a lot of information, but it is easy to plan, execute, analyze and report a usability evaluation for DSL using it. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

17. PEOU5. Browsing Usa-DSL Process pages is easy. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

18. PEOU6. It is easy to find the necessary elements to perform usability evaluation for DSL in the Usa-DSL Process. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

19. PEOU7. Interaction with the process requires a little of my mental effort. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

20. PEOU8. Overall, I find the Usa-DSL Process is ease to used. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Open Questions

Please, describe as much as you can in each of the following questions.

21. PO1. What is your opinion/statement on the Usa-DSL Process for developing and conducting a usability evaluation for DSL? Please, provide details in your answer.

22. PO2. Would you adopt Usa-DSL Process evaluating the usability of a DSL?
Please, provide details in your answer.

23. PO3. Would you recommend a colleague Usa-DSL Process to support performing usability evaluation for DSL? Please, provide details in your answer.

Thank you for your
time and opinion.

Please help with our research by sharing this link on your social network or by email to your colleagues

<http://tiny.cc/usa-DSLFacebook>

<http://tiny.cc/Usa-DSLTwitter>

<http://tiny.cc/Usa-DSLLinkedIn>

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